

Advanced Machining Dynamics Simulation

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ABSTRACT

Chatter is one of the main limitations to milling performances. Prediction of such unstable phenomenon via stability lobe diagrams requires the measurement of the Frequency Response Functions (FRFs) for each tool and machine tool setup. This paper presents a hybrid FE-experimental approach to identify tool-tip FRFs with only one set of measurements, taking into account tool change without any other experimental test. Machine tool dynamics is modeled using a Finite Element (FE) approach. Machine, spindle and tool-holder are described by a lumped model characterized by frequency-dependent stiffness, while the tool is FE modeled. Lumped model and tool are connected by means of stiffness matrices extracted using the Craig-Bampton dynamic reduction method. The obtained simplified model of machine tool enables chatter prediction by means of stability lobe diagram for different tool without the need for extensive experimentation. Once a new tool is clamped no other measurements are needed, just the new tool FE model. Experimental validation under different conditions is provided, showing accuracy and reliability of proposed approach.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Milling is the most widespread manufacturing technology to produce final shape metal components. In the last decades optimization of such process has been carried out considering different issues, such as cutting lubrication (Qin et al., 2012), environmental impact (Campatelli et al., 2015), surface integrity (Duan and Hao, 2014). However performances of this technology are still limited by self-excited chatter vibration occurrence. This regenerative phenomenon is particularly dangerous because it grows as result of dynamic modulation of chip thickness, leading to unstable variation of cutting force and consequently tool motion, resulting in poor surface finish, increase of tool wear and possible tool breakage. Chatter has been widely studied: Quintana and Ciurana (2011) and Altintas and Weck (2004) presented two comprehensive reviews on the topic. Several approaches aiming at both detecting (Grossi et al., 2015c), and suppressing (Madoliat et al., 2011) the phenomenon have been developed, however the intrinsic experimental nature of such techniques is not suitable for forecasting and process planning purpose. Therefore extensive investigations on predictive approaches have been carried out. Graphic chart showing the stable conditions as a function of depth of cut and spindle speed, known as Stability Lobe Diagram (SLD), is the most common result of chatter prediction analysis. This diagram is used to select optimal operating conditions (i.e., cutting parameters) in order to avoid chatter (Altintas and Budak, 1995; Kurata et al., 2010). To create SLD, machine tool dynamics at the tool-tip and the cutting forces generated by the process must be investigated. For what concern cutting forces many parameters can influence the reliability of cutting force models adopted in the stability method such as spindle speed (Grossi et al., 2014, 2015b) and tool wear (Afazov et al., 2013). Regarding the system response this is obtained generally by experimental test directly on the machine tool (Matsumura et al., 2008). This technique, known as Experimental Modal Analysis (EMA), is the most reliable approach but it is expensive and time consuming. In fact, machine dynamics may change significantly with a new tool clamped to the spindle, because tool is generally the most

flexible part of the assembly, and it is more apt to vibrate. As a result, the modal test has to be performed for every tooling system used, limiting chatter prediction technique industrial diffusion.

For that reason analytical-experimental methods are deeply studied, in order to implement predictive models able to identify dynamics of different spindle-holder and tool configurations with the minimum set of measurements. This is possible through the substructure analysis: impedance and receptance coupling (RCSA) techniques, borrowed from structural engineering, allow to eliminate time consuming and repetitive FRF tests for each tool. This approach was firstly implemented by Schmitz et al. (Schmitz and Donalson, 2000) to assembly the dynamics of the spindle-holder assembly and the tool using the dynamic behavior of the holder-tool joint. These techniques need accurate identification of dynamic behavior of each substructure and joints connecting them (especially between tool and tool-holder) in order to provide accurate results. Initially Schmitz et al. (Schmitz and Donalson, 2000) considered only translational motion of the substructures, ignoring tool rotational flexibilities in modeling, reducing significantly accuracy of the method.

Park et al. (Park et al., 2003) presented an improved receptance coupling technique introducing rotational FRFs: the end mill is modeled numerically as a cylindrical beam, and the FRF of the spindle-tool-holder system is identified using impact modal tests at the two different blank cylinders free end clamped on the tool-holder. The use of calibration tools allows the determination of rotational responses using inverse receptance coupling (IRCSA). Thanks to the full FRF matrix, dynamic behavior of machine can be obtained accurately with any desired new tool, but two experimental set-ups are required instead of one. Other researchers (Albertelli et al., 2013; Mancisidor et al., 2014) tried to improve Park's work: however in all the cases rotational FRFs are identified by an experimental phase with a calibration tool, increasing time required by the method.

Different kind of tool models are used in receptance coupling method: Schmitz (Schmitz and Donalson, 2000) starts using Euler-Bernoulli beam but subsequently Timoshenko beam (Ertürk et al., 2006) was found more accurate for dynamics application. In addition some studies (e.g., (Albertelli et al., 2013)) used finite element (FE) solid element in case beam model fails to accurately model tool and tool-holder geometry. Besides receptance coupling methods other hybrid modeling approaches have been developed: Catania et al. (Catania and Mancinelli, 2011) presented milling machine model obtained by coupling experimentally evaluated modal model of milling machine frame and spindle with an analytical discrete model of the tool, based on the continuous free-free beam shape analytical eigenfunctions. Also in their work an extensive experimental procedure is required to validate machine model.

In this paper an innovative approach based on finite element modeling of machine tool is presented. A lumped model of machine including tool-holder is experimentally characterized and coupled with an accurate FE model of the tool. Method is fully developed in FE environment allowing to include any kind of FE tool model, either beam, solid or a mix of both. Holder-tool contact stiffness is identified using holder FE model and modal reduction technique. Developed method can accurately predict entire machine tool dynamics starting from only one series of measurements on the machine without tool clamped, eliminating repetitive FRF measurements of each tool attached to the spindle-tool-holder system. Number of tests are thus significantly reduced compared to standard EMA approach and even compared to common RCSA approaches (Albertelli et al., 2013; Park et al., 2003): in the proposed method no calibration tests are needed, only machine tool FRF response.

2. PROPOSED APPROACH

Proposed method has been developed considering machine tool flexibility condensed in a simplified model. The starting point is hence the modeling of the machine tool dynamics by means of a lumped model, experimentally characterized by a set of FRFs measurements on the tool-holder clamped to the spindle, without any tool. Frequency dependent springs are used to fulfill this task. Tool-tip FRF is then obtained coupling the lumped model with the FE model of the specific tool considered. Lumped model is connected with the tool by means of likely stiffness extracted by a numerical Craig-Bampton modal reduction (Bampton and Craig, 1968) performed on the tool-holder in free-free configuration. To implement the proposed model are therefore required:

- A set of measurement on tool-holder clamped on the machine, no other calibration measurements are needed.
- FE model of tool-holder and tool

Starting from these inputs, proposed approach allows to identify tool-tip FRF to be used in chatter stability analysis. A flow chart of the proposed method is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flow chart of the proposed method

2.1 Machine tool lumped model

The lumped model is chosen as simple as possible: a two-degree of freedom (DOF) model is selected as the simplest one able to take into account the rotational DOF that cannot be neglected for accurate FRF identification at the tool-tip (Park et al., 2003). Frequency dependent springs are used in order to match, with a simple lumped model, the dynamic behavior of the machine tool. The proposed model is composed by two masses rigidly connected and three grounded frequency dependent stiffness springs: two translational (K_1 e K_2) and one rotational (K_θ) that constrain the model, lumped model is presented in Figure 2 where θ is the relative rotation between point 1 and 2.

Figure 2. Lumped model scheme

Model is thus described by three complex stiffness characterized by structural damping, complex stiffness K is presented in Eq. 1:

$$K_j(f) = k_j(f)(1 + ih_j) \quad (1)$$

where capital K is the complex stiffness composed by stiffness k and structural damping h .

For each frequency (f) the stiffness are calculated on the basis of experimental measurements performed on the machine tool with only the tool-holder clamped on the spindle. Two points on tool-holder are chosen to measure dynamic response (FRFs) and distance between points is measured. To obtain an equivalent lumped model the experimental receptance matrix (G) is required. The complete receptance matrix includes rotational DOF response. Rotational FRFs are hardly obtainable via experimental tests. To simplify the receptance matrix, a rigid connection is

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included between the two masses, this allows avoid rational FRF measurements: θ angle is identified through nodes translations as:

$$\theta = (x_2 - x_1) / l \quad (2)$$

where x_1 and x_2 are the translational displacements and l is distance between the two masses, chosen equal to the one between the two measurements points. Equation 2 is valid as long as segment between point 1 and point 2 is considered rigid. This is an acceptable approximation: proximity of the points and stiffness of tool-holders suggest this behavior in the frequency range of interest (i.e., within 20kHz).

The result of this approximation is a 2x2 matrix composed by translational FRFs. Three FRFs should be then measured: Point 1 driving point (G_{11}), Point 2 driving point (G_{22}) and cross Points 1 and 2 (G_{12}):

$$[G(f)] = \begin{bmatrix} G_{11}(f) & G_{12}(f) \\ G_{12}(f) & G_{22}(f) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

These FRFs are used to extract lumped model parameters (mass, stiffness and damping) according to the following formulas:

$$[H(f)] = [G(f)]^{-1} \quad (4)$$

$$[K(f)] = [H(f)]^{-1} + M(2\pi f)^2 \quad \text{where:} \quad (5)$$

$$[M] = \begin{bmatrix} m_{01} & 0 \\ 0 & m_{02} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$[K(f)] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{K_0(f)}{l} & -\frac{K_0(f)}{l} \\ -\frac{K_0(f)}{l} & \frac{K_0(f)}{l} + \frac{K_1(f)}{l} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

No univocal solution for the system can be obtained: more than one equivalent lumped model can be found. In this paper mass values are fixed and frequency dependent stiffness hence calculated according to the equations 8, 9 and 10:

$$K_0(f) = k_0(f)(1 + ih_0) = -l^2 H_{12}(f) \quad (8)$$

$$K_1(f) = k_1(f)(1 + ih_1) = H_{11} - K_0 / l^2 + m_1(2\pi f)^2 \quad (9)$$

$$K_2(f) = k_2(f)(1 + ih_2) = H_{22} - K_0 / l^2 + m_2(2\pi f)^2 \quad (10)$$

In this way thanks to real and imaginary part of H , for each frequency, stiffness (k) and structural damping (h) can be calculated to be included in the lumped model. Stiffness and mass matrices values are not physically related to the machine structure but allow the lumped model to be dynamically equivalent to the milling machine without tool in the two connection points. Thanks to frequency dependent stiffness, a simple 2 DOFs model can accurately represent machine dynamic behavior generally characterized by a large number of modes.

2.2 Tool model

The proposed method requires tool-holder and tool FE model. The method is fully implemented in FE environment; therefore any kind of FE elements can be used (e.g. beam, solid). In order to apply proposed approach to any tool clamped to the machine with only one measurement set-up, also tool-holder is included in the modeling approach. Tool-holder FE model is essential for the method: this component is the link between machine and tool, i.e., experimental measurements and numerical model.

2.3 Machine-tool connection

Connection between FE tool and lumped model is obtained using the Craig-Bampton modal reduction (Bampton and Craig, 1968) of the connection component (tool-holder). Thanks to this modal reduction technique, it is possible to extract mass and stiffness matrices of component described simply by nodes of interest. In this application the FE model of the tool-holder in free-free configuration should be reduced to:

- Connection nodes with lumped model, positioned in the measurements points.
- Interface nodes between tool-holder and tool.

In this way connection technique allows to identify a likely contact stiffness between machine and tool and to consider any kind of connection between tool-holder and tool. Only stiffness matrix is extracted from modal reduction, mass is not needed because already included in the experimental tests and thus in the lumped model. A scheme of the connection nodes is reported in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Connection scheme

3. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

Proposed approach has been experimentally validated on a Mori Seiki NMV 1500 DCG milling machine using a DIEBOLD HSK 32E R16x60 tool-holder with collet chuck connection. An ISCAR Multi-Master shank has been used as tool.

3.1 Experimental characterization of lumped model

Tool-holder was mounted on the machine without tool (no collet, nut and shank are attached). Experimental Modal Analysis (EMA) was performed on two points in the positions presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. a) Experimental set-up for lumped model definition b) Tool-holder detail with the two accelerometers

Two accelerometers (PCB 352C22) have been attached to the tool-holder and FRFs measurements have been performed by means of impact hammer (Brüel & Kjær 8202). Both driving and cross FRFs have been acquired with only one measurements set up. Starting from these measurements lumped model is created: nodes distance l has been chosen equal to distance between the two measurements points (19.6 mm), fictitious masses (m_1 and m_2) have been set equal to half total tool-holder mass (0.086 kg). Frequency variable stiffness and damping values have been calculated according to proposed method (Eq. 8, 9, 10).

Once lumped model was created a direct FRFs simulations was performed using MSC Nastran, to compare dynamic behavior between experimental and lumped model. Results, presented in Figure 5, confirm dynamic equivalence between lumped model and machine tool experimental response, as imposed.

Figure 5. FRFs comparison between lumped model and experimental machine tool

3.2 FE tool model

Tooling system is composed by: a HSK32 collet chuck tool-holder, tapered collet, nut, 8 mm shank with cutting insert. 3D solid FE elements is used to model tool-holder and tool because beam elements fail to model properly collect connection (Grossi et al., 2015a). Preliminary sensitivity studies have been conducted in order to get a suitable balance between computational time and accuracy of the numerical simulations. The mesh size has been chosen smaller than required by convergence analysis, to achieve a better components geometry description. Interchangeable cutting head that can be added to the shank is modeled as a lumped mass. Tool-holder and tool assembly, its FE model and components are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Finite element models of the tooling assembly

In table 1 the values for steel and carbide used in the numerical simulation (a damping ratio value of 0.005 has been chosen for each component) are summarized.

Table 1. Mechanical characteristics of the materials used in the simulation

	Type	Material	Modulus (N/mm ²)	Density (kg/m ³)	Poisson coefficient
Tool-holder	HSK32E	Steel	2.0×10^{11}		0.3
Nut	-	Steel	2.1×10^{11}		0.3
Tapered Collet	R16 – $\Phi 8$	Steel	2.0×10^{11}		0.25
Tool	Shank 110mm – $\Phi 8$	Carbide	6.6×10^{11}	13466	0.24

This validation and optimization procedure has been carried out in order to present method results without the effect of inaccuracy of FE model of the tool. Adjustment of material proprieties is therefore not required in general. Nevertheless, in the same way of every method based on FE model, an accurate model is required to return accurate results.

3.3 Coupling and validation

Lumped model and tool model are connected via stiffness extracted from reduced tool-holder model to interface nodes with collet and connection nodes positioned in measurements points. Tool-holder reduction nodes are presented in white in Figure 7a.

Figure 7. a) Tool-holder reduction nodes b) Simplified machine tool model

Thanks to this likely stiffness a simplified hybrid experimental-FE model of the machine is created, shown in Figure 7b. Machine tool model allows predicting dynamics at the tool-tip for chatter stability analysis. Simulated results were experimentally verified. Impact tests have been performed on machine tool at the tool-tip, with different overhang (86.1 and 70.7 mm), with and without the interchangeable cutting head (Figure 8). A Brüel & Kjaer Type 8202 impulse hammer, LMS Scadas III frontend, LMS Test.Lab 11A software, and PCB 352C22 accelerometers (0.4 g) have been used.

Figure 8. a) FRF set-up on the shank without cutting head b) FRF set-up with cutting head

The comparison shows an excellent agreement between numerical and experimental FRFs, as reported in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Experimental and simulated tool-tip FRFs.

FRFs prediction is accurate in a very large frequency range (till 8192Hz), although some discrepancies are detected at high frequency and for what concerns damping. This could be caused by FE model inaccuracies (more significant at high frequency) and FE model damping modeling not analyzed deeply in this paper.

3.4 Stability prediction

Tool-tip FRFs simulated can be used for stability prediction. In this section Stability Lobe Diagram (SLD) according to Altintas' theory (Altintas and Budak, 1995) are calculated with both experimental and numerical FRFs in order to present chatter prediction capability of the proposed method. Tool-holder and tool presented for validation is used: 70.7mm overhang and cutting insert is considered (2 flutes, 8 mm diameter). A side milling operation on Aluminum 7075-T6 (cutting coefficients $K_{tc}=796$ MPa, $K_{rc}=196$ MPa) at 1 mm radial depth of cut is simulated. Results are shown in Figure 10 in which stability lobe diagrams for measured and predicted FRFs are plotted.

Figure 10: Comparison between stability lobes obtained by experimentally measured FRF and predicted FRF

SLD calculated with predicted FRF is in agreement with experimental one: differences are related mainly to a small lack of damping in the FRFs, causing discrepancies in depth of cut limit. Lobe positioning is accurately predicted, allowing optimal spindle speed selection.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper a hybrid FE-experimental model that uses an experimental characterization of machine tool dynamics at the tool-holder, coupled together to a FE representation of the tool has been developed. The tests carried out using this approach in different conditions (e.g. overhang) have proven a good capability to predict FRF of the machine at the tool-tip. The proposed method improves the accuracy of previous receptance coupling techniques by taking into account rotational degrees of freedom at the tool and contact stiffness. Only one measurement set-up on the machine without tool is required, no other calibration tests are needed, expanding industrial relevance thanks to its flexibility.

Presented approach allows estimating chatter stability diagrams accurately, minimizing time-consuming experimental tests. Moreover, compared to other approaches this method does not directly obtain FRFs, but build a hybrid model in FE environment. Therefore, the scope of this new simplified model could be extended to other applications such as time-domain simulation or flexible multi-body system.

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